

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF HIGH-RISE DIAGRID STRUCTURES WITH DIFFERENT PLAN SHAPES (RECTANGULAR AND PLUS SHAPE) IN SEISMIC ZONE III UNDER STATIC, RESPONSE SPECTRUM AND WIND ANALYSIS

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Abstract:-

High-rise buildings are increasingly being constructed in urban areas due to rapid population growth and limited land availability. The structural system plays a significant role in ensuring the stability, safety, and efficiency of such tall structures. Among the modern structural systems, the diagrid system has gained significant attention because of its ability to efficiently resist lateral loads through a network of diagonal members, reducing the requirement of conventional vertical columns. The diagrid system improves structural stiffness, architectural flexibility, and overall performance of high-rise buildings under seismic and wind forces.

This study presents a comparative analysis of high-rise buildings with diagrid structural systems having different plan configurations, namely rectangular and plus (+) shapes, located in Seismic Zone III. The primary objective of the study is to evaluate and compare the structural behavior of these plan shapes under lateral loads. The analysis is carried out by considering the same building height and structural parameters for both configurations to ensure a consistent basis for comparison.

Key Words: - High-Rise Building, Diagrid System, Plan Shape Configuration, Seismic Zone III, Wind Analysis, Story Drift

1. Introduction:-

The rapid growth in population and high cost of land has great impact on the construction industry and this tends to the construction of buildings in upward direction. But as the height of buildings increases lateral load resisting system becomes more important than the structural system that resists gravity loads. For resisting those lateral loads some common systems are used such as: rigid frame, shear wall, wall-frame, braced tube system, outrigger system and tubular system. Recently the diagonal grid structural system has been widely used for tall buildings due to its structural efficiency and aesthetic potential provided by the unique geometric configuration of the system. The configuration and efficiency of a diagrid system reduces the number of the structural element required on the outer side of the buildings, therefore less obstruction to

the outside view. The diagrid system structural efficiency also helps in avoiding interior and corner columns and therefore allowing significant flexibility with the floorplan. The latest high rise building system which now has become most favourable among today's designer is the "Diagonal Grid System" also called as "Diagrid system". Diagrid system consists of many diagonal structures that connect together to form a triangulated shape or can be seen as grid shape. Recently the diagrid system has been applied to several tall steel buildings because of its structural efficiency. Diagrid is particular form of space truss, which does not have any conventional column on the exterior periphery of the structure.

2. Problem statement for validation:-

The present study includes the design and behaviour of high rise buildings with diagrid

systems. Analysis and compare the results of 48 storey diagrid structure of plus(+), rectangular and L-shape shape of buildings for parameters like Storey shear, storey displacement & storey drift. Also, to find optimum diagrid angle for 2-storey,4-storey,6-storey & 8-storey modules of plus(+), rectangular and L-shape shape of building of same height is located in zone III seismic zone.

3. Review of previous studies:

M. M. Ali and K. Moon (May 2007): “**Structural performance and constructability issues of diagrid structures employed for complex-shaped tall buildings such as twisted, tilted and freeform towers**”. In this study includes Structural performance and constructability issues of diagrid structures employed for complex-shaped tall buildings such as twisted, tilted and freeform towers Though widely used today, application of diagrid structures for tall buildings is relatively new. With abundant emergence of complex-shaped tall buildings all over the world, more studies on their potential structural systems and multidisciplinary collaboration are very much required to construct built environments of higher performance.

Barry Charnish (June 2008): “**Study of structural design of a building**”. In this Study of structural design of a building in Calgary and Western Canada. The project of sixty-nine floors high rise building named as “Bow” made for EnCana Corporation with a height approximately equals to 247 meters. The developer team requirements a unique design of tower which gives a benefit to both the occupants and residents of Calgary. And also wants a decrease in energy consumption as associated with conventional towers. The tower involves of a trussed tube fabricated of diagonal grids on their perimeter which includes six storey diagrids laterally curved south and north elevations.

K. S. Moon (June 2011) : “**Study of the structural performance of the diagrid systems in complex shaped tall**

buildings”. The complex shaped tall building models considered for the study was twisted tower, tilted towers and freeform towers. The complex shaped tall building models were designed with diagrid systems, and their structural performance and efficiency potential was studied. For the study of impacts for variation of geometric configurations of complex shaped tall buildings. Parametric structural models were used for the study of rate of twisting and angle of tilting. On the basis of results obtained, design considerations are studied for using the diagrid system efficiently in complex shaped tall buildings.

K. Jani and P. V. Patel (May 2013) : “**Analysed and designed diagrid structural system for high rise steel buildings**”. A 36 storey diagrid steel building was adopted for the study. Also, 50, 60, 70 and 80 storey diagrid steel structures are analysed and designed for the investigation. ETABS software was used for modelling and analyses of the structure. All the members of the structure were designed using IS 800:2007. All the load combinations were considered during design and analyses of the model. Structural design of the building was governed by lateral loads due to wind or earthquake. It was observed that most of the lateral load was resisted by diagrid columns on the periphery, while gravity load was resisted by both the internal columns and the peripheral diagonal columns. So internal columns should be designed for the vertical load only.

T Bhuiyan (May 2016) : “**To determine the optimal member sizes and shape for diagrid assemblies**”. Studied 03 buildings with 38, 64, 82 storeys with height 133 m, 224 m & 287 m and with plan size 33 m x 33 m, 52 m x 35.5 m and 48 m x 48 m respectively. Some iterations were done to determine the optimal member sizes and shape for diagrid assemblies. Both the earthquake and wind actions were taken into account for checking the member sizes sustainability. Several design assumptions were used such as the constant inclination of braces along the height of the structure, uniform bending and shear

strain distribution along the height of structure and wind drift of $H/500$ should be achieved.

Dr. Gopisiddappa et al.(June 2017) : “**The comparison between linear building and diagrid building is carried out**”.The present work consists of analysis of 30 storey linear building and analysis of diagrid systems with different diagonal angles that is 45 degree, 63 degree, 73 degree, 75 degree, 78 degree, 81 degree. The comparison between linear building and diagrid building is carried out. ETABS software is used for modelling and analysis of structure. Analysis results like displacement, interstorey drift are presented here. The conclusion was made that the region 63 degree to 75 degree (diagonal angle) diagrid system possess better stiffness, storey drift and storey displacement are less in this region.

Trupti A. Kinjawadekar and Amit C. Kinjawadekar(May 2018) : “**Dynamic analysis is carried out on both types of model for the terms like, Storey displacements, storey drifts, time period and base shear**”. Worked on the two set of models were taken as 18 storey and other 36 storey models with three different angles namely, 45° , 64° and 72° . Number of storeys in each type of module is decided the angle of diagrid. The conventional building model of 90° angle of diagrid is also prepared. The geometry of model is taken as bay width of 12m and storey height as 3m. To study the seismic behaviour of diagrid members SAP- 2016 software is used. Dynamic analysis is carried out on both types of model for the terms like, Storey displacements, storey drifts, time period and base shear.

4. Modeling & Analysis:-

The present study includes the design and behaviour of high rise buildings with diagrid systems. Analysis and compare the results of 48 storey diagrid structure of plus(+), rectangular shape shape of buildings for parameters like Storey shear, storey displacement & storey drift. Also, to find

optimum diagrid angle for 2-storey,4-storey,6-storey & 8-storey modules of plus(+), rectangular and L-shape shape of building of same height is located in zone III seismic zone.

Figure: Plan of Plus(+) shape building model

Above Figure shows the typical plan of Plus(+) shape building models which are considered for the study Number of bays in X and Y directions are 12 as shown in figure and spacing between each bay is 4 meters.

Figure: Plan of rectangular shape building model

Above Figure shows the typical plan of rectangular shape building models which are considered for the study as shown in figure and spacing between each bay is 4 meters. The

building is subjected to following Loads as per IS 875 (part 1 and 2)-2015: Dead load: 2 kN/m² · Live Load: 3 kN/m²

The following table shows that basic design consideration in seismic zone III.

Zone	Zone factor	Location of building	Basic wind speed of city in m/s	Soil type
III	0.16	Pune	39	Hard(site type 1)

Figure:- 3D rendered view of plus(+) shape structure

Figure:- Top View of Plus (+) Shape

Figure:- 3D rendered view of rectangular shape structure

5. Section properties for plus(+), rectangular shape of building in zone III:-

All sections properties have been same in each shape of building in zone III. For beams the Indian standard wide flange beam sections are used and for columns steel tubes are used. For diagrid members steel pipes are used.

Below Table shows the section properties for all storey module of building

model with diagrid systems.

Story	Beam	Column [tube section]	Diagrid [pipe section]
1-16	ISMB 550	750 X 750 X 50	750 X 25
17-32	ISMB 500	700 X 700 X 45	750X 25
33-48	ISMB 500	600 X 600 X 35	750 X25

Table: Section properties for Plus(+), rectangular shape of building in zone III

Below Table shows the values of diagrid angles for the respective storey modules of plus(+) shape of structure. As the storey module increases the angle of diagrid increases. Diagrid angles taken for the study are varies from 41° to 74°

Number storeys per module	Angle
2	41.18°
4	60.25°
6	69.14°
8	74.05°

Table: Diagrid angle for plus (+) shape of building

6. Load Combinations:-

There are different types of load combinations are considered which are given below in table

Load case No.	Load case details
1	1.5(D.L+L.L)
2	1.2(D.L+L.L+ EQ-X)
3	1.2(D.L+L.L- EQ-X)
4	1.2(D.L+L.L+ EQ-Y)
5	1.2(D.L+L.L- EQ-Y)
6	1.5(D.L+ EQ-X)
7	1.5(D.L- EQ-X)

8	1.5(D.L+ EQ-Y)
9	1.5(D.L- EQ-X)
10	0.9D.L+ 1.5EQ-X
11	0.9D.L- 1.5EQ-X
12	0.9D.L+ 1.5EQ-Y
13	0.9D.L- 1.5EQ-Y
14	1.2(D.L+L.L+ WL-X)
15	1.2(D.L+L.L- WL-X)
16	1.2(D.L+L.L+ WL-Y)
17	1.2(D.L+L.L- WL-Y)
18	1.5(D.L+ WL-X)
19	1.5(D.L- WL-X)
20	1.5(D.L+ WL-Y)
21	1.5(D.L- WL-Y)
22	0.9D.L+ 1.5WL-X
23	0.9D.L-1.5WL-X
24	0.9D.L+ 1.5WL-Y
25	0.9D.L- 1.5WL-Y
26	1.2(D.L+L.L+ RS-X)
27	1.2(D.L+L.L- RS-X)
28	1.2(D.L+L.L+ RS-Y)
29	1.2(D.L+L.L- RS-Y)
30	1.5(D.L+ RS-X)
31	1.5(D.L- RS-X)
32	1.5(D.L+ RS-Y)
33	1.5(D.L- RS-Y)
34	0.9D.L+ 1.5RS-X
35	0.9D.L- 1.5RS-X
36	0.9D.L+ 1.5RS-Y
37	0.9D.L- 1.5RS-Y

All load combinations are selected during analysis of story modules in seismic zone III. The load combinations mentioned in table are selected in ETABS using default steel structure

combination

7. Result Analysis:-

Analysis Result and its Discussion for Plus(+) shape of building in Seismic Zone III Seismic zone is having zone factor value 0.16. Site types taken as 1. Importance factor taken as 1.5 because our structure is included in importance service. For the wind load consideration structure location is taken in Pune city and according to that basic wind speed is considered which is 39 m/s. purpose of diagrid structure is for hospital so mean probable design life of structure is 100 years and on the basis of that risk coefficient is considered which is 1.06. Category of our structure is 3. Structural class is taken as C because maximum dimension that is height of structure is more than 50 m. k4 factor is taken as 1.30 which is taken as per type of structure. Windward and leeward coefficients taken as 0.8 and 0.6 respectively. Response spectrum analysis is used dynamic analysis. In which SSRS and CQC method are considered. Damping ratio is taken as 5%. For wind analysis in ETABS exposure from extent of diaphragms method is used. First all scale factor is considered with is code recommendation and dynamic base shear is less than 80% of static base shear so it was changed.

Figure : Maximum storey displacement for all modules in zone III

Above Figure shows the graphical representation of maximum storey

displacement of 48 storey building modules in zone III. This is the graphical representation for wind load analysis because wind load analysis gives maximum values of story displacement in zone II as compare to seismic and response spectrum analysis. Graph is plotted for modules vs maximum storey displacement.

The maximum storey displacement is higher in 8 module diagrid which is 245.48 mm. The smallest value of maximum storey displacement is 187.2 mm which is observed for four storey module. It is observed that least value of maximum story displacement falls between 60^0 to 70^0 . Maximum permissible storey displacement is 336 mm and it is observed that maximum story displacement for all modules in zone III are within the permissible limit. When we compare eight module diagrid with four and six module diagrid the maximum story displacement for four module and six module diagrid is reduced by 23.74% and 14.83%.

Figure: Maximum storey drift for all modules in zone III

Above Fig shows the graphical representation of maximum storey drift of 48 storey building modules in zone III. Graph is plotted for modules vs maximum storey drift. This is the graphical representation for wind load analysis because wind load analysis gives maximum values of story drift in zone III as compare to seismic and response spectrum analysis. The maximum storey drift is higher in eight module which is 0.001839 m. The least

value of maximum storey drift is 0.001317 m which is found in four storey module diagrid. Maximum permissible storey drift is 0.014 m. and it is observed that maximum story drift for all modules in zone III are within the permissible limit. When we compare eight module diagrid with four and six module diagrid the maximum story drift for four module and six module diagrid is reduced by 28.38% and 15.82%.

8. Conclusion:-

The study evaluates the maximum storey displacement of a 48-storey diagrid building for different module configurations under wind load in Seismic Zone III. From the graphical representation of modules versus maximum storey displacement, it is observed that wind load analysis produces higher displacement values compared to static and response spectrum analysis. Among the considered configurations, the 8-storey module diagrid shows the highest maximum storey displacement of 245.48 mm, whereas the 4-storey module diagrid exhibits the lowest displacement of 187.2 mm. The results indicate that the least values of storey displacement occur in the range between 60° to 70° height levels, demonstrating comparatively better lateral stability for smaller module configurations.

The analysis of maximum storey drift for the 48-storey diagrid building in Seismic Zone III under wind load is presented through a graphical comparison of different module configurations. The graph plotted between modules and maximum storey drift shows that wind load analysis produces higher storey drift values compared to static and response spectrum analysis.

From the results, the 8-storey module diagrid exhibits the maximum storey drift of 0.001839 m, while the 4-storey module diagrid shows the minimum storey drift of 0.001317 m. This indicates that smaller module configurations provide better lateral stiffness and structural stability.

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